

Vanadium. Part VII. Vanadium(IV) Complexes of Benziminazoles and Oxine-*N*-oxide

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Preparation and properties of the complexes of the ligands: benziminazole (I) (RH), 2-guanidino-benziminazole (R'H) (II), benziminazole-2-carboxylic acid (R'' H) (III), and oxine-*N*-oxide (R''' H) (IV) with quadrivalent vanadium are described. (I) produces a blue $[\text{VO}(\text{RH})_4 \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{SO}_4$; (II) yields two compounds: (a) ash-coloured $[\text{VO}(\text{RH})_2(\text{O})]\text{NO}_4$, (b) rose-red $[\text{VO}(\text{R}')_2]$; (III) affords bluish green $[\text{VO}(\text{R}'')_2]\text{H}_2\text{O}$; (IV) produces olive-green $[\text{VO}(\text{R}''')_2]$. These complexes are all paramagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.50-1.77\text{B.M.}$).

Some metallic derivatives of benziminazole were reported by Feigl and Gleich¹. Ghosh² reported two complexes with bivalent copper: (1) blue, unstable, tetrakis-benziminazole-copper(II) sulphate, (2) red, stable bis-benziminazole-copper (II). In the first of these, benziminazole functions as a neutral unidentate ligand, whereas in the second case it behaves as a monobasic bidentate unit. Chelates with Ni(II) and Co(II) were also described by the same author².

Vanadyl sulphate reacts with excess of benziminazole in aqueous ethanol medium to furnish a beautiful, silky, sky-blue crystalline precipitate, corresponding to $[\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{RH})_4]\text{SO}_4$ (where RH = a molecule of benziminazole). Benziminazole evidently functions here as a neutral monodentate ligand. The substance is paramagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.63\text{B.M.}$).

Since the early works of Dubský *et al.*³ on metal complexes of 2-guanidinobenziminazole (erroneously called *c*-phenylene-biguanide by the authors), Banerjee and Ghosh⁴ recently described some more co-ordination complexes of the ligand with Cu (II) and Ni (II). In all these complexes, the ligand behaved as a bidentate unit.

Vanadium(IV) forms two different types of complexes with this ligand: (i) Vanadyl sulphate and the ligand in aqueous ethanol medium in approximately 1:1 ratio and at pH 4-5 afford crystalline, light ash-coloured precipitate, $[\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{RH})]\text{SO}_4$ (where RH = a molecule of 2-guanidinobenziminazole). The ligand, 2-guanidinobenziminazole functions here as a neutral bidentate unit. The water molecule is lost at above 200°, so that it may be reasonably considered that it is inside the co-ordination zone. This gives a low paramagnetic value ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.50\text{B.M.}$). (ii) Vanadyl sulphate and a large excess of the ligand at pH around 6-7 furnish a rose-red, glistening, crystalline precipitate, $[\text{VO}(\text{R}')_2]$ (B) ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.59\text{B.M.}$).

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1. *Monatsh.*, 1928, **49**, 385.
2. *This Journal*, 1951, **28**, 710.
3. *Chem. Abs.*, 1938, **32**, 4472.
4. *This Journal*, 1961, **38**, 237.

Benzimidazole-2-carboxylic acid produces light bluish green crystals with VOSO_4 . The compound has the composition $[\text{VO}(\text{R}''')_2]\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (where $\text{R}''' \text{H}$ = a molecule of benzimidazole-2-carboxylic acid). The water molecule is lost readily. The compound gives a moment value of 1.61 B.M.

Vanadyl sulphate reacts with oxine-*N*-oxide at pH 2-3 to furnish a deep olive-green crystalline precipitate of the composition $[\text{VO}(\text{R}''')_2]$ [where $\text{R}''' \text{H}$ = a molecule of oxine-*N*-oxide). The compound is paramagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.77$ B.M.). Its poor solubility in benzene did not permit any determination of its molecular weight.

TABLE I

Magnetic measurements.

No.	Compound.	$\chi_M(\text{corr.})$	Diamagnetic correction $\times 10^6$.	μ_{eff} [B.M.].	Temp.
1	$[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)_4\text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{SO}_4$	1073.0	313.0	1.63	35°
2	$[\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_3)\text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{SO}_4$	922.5	135.8	1.50	30°
3	$[\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{N}_3)_2]$	1023.0	147.8	1.59	35°
4	$[\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_3\text{O}_2)_2]\text{H}_2\text{O}$	1047.0	168.7	1.60	32°
5	$[\text{VO}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{NO}_2)_2]$	1282.0	188.4	1.77	31°

EXPERIMENTAL

Benzimidazole was prepared by following the method of Ghosh⁵. 2-Guanidinobenzimidazole was prepared according to King *et al.*⁵. Benzimidazole-2-carboxylic acid was prepared by oxidation of 2-hydroxymethylbenzimidazole with KMnO_4 . Oxine-*N*-oxide was prepared according to Bhat and Jain⁶.

5. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1366.

6. *This Journal*, 1961, 38, 327

Aquo-oxo-tetrakis-benziminazole-vanadium (IV) Sulphate.—Benziminazole (1.4 g.), dissolved in ethanol (25 ml), was added to an aqueous solution of VOSO_4 (0.5 g. in 5-10 ml water) and the mixture was refluxed on a water bath for about 2 hr. The sky-blue, silky, crystalline precipitate formed at pH (ca.) 3-4 was then filtered, washed well with ethanol, and dried in vacuum over CaCl_2 . This is insoluble in ethanol, benzene, etc. {Found: V, 7.85; N, 17.32; SO_4 , 14.68; H_2O (by loss at 130°), 3.00. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}] \cdot \text{SO}_4$ requires V, 7.81; N, 17.15; SO_4 , 14.70; H_2O , 2.75%}.

Aquo-oxo-mono-2-guanidino-benziminazole-vanadium (IV) Sulphate.—A warm ethanolic solution of 2-guanidinobenziminazole (0.7 g. in 20 ml ethanol) was slowly added to an aqueous solution of VOSO_4 (0.5 g. in 10 ml water) and the pH adjusted to about 4-5 with dilute acetic acid. The ash-coloured crystalline precipitate separating was refluxed on a water bath for about 2-3 hr. This was then filtered, washed well with ethanol, and dried in vacuum over CaCl_2 . {Found: V, 14.30; N, 19.80; SO_4 , 26.20; H_2O (by loss at 210°), 3.90. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_3) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}] \cdot \text{SO}_4$ requires V, 14.33; N, 19.60; SO_4 , 26.96; H_2O , 5.05%}.

Oxo-bis-2-guanidinobenziminazole-vanadium (IV).—An aqueous solution of VOSO_4 (0.12 g. in 2 ml water) was added to a warm ethanolic solution of 2-guanidinobenziminazole (1g. in 20 ml ethanol). A rose-red, crystalline precipitate appeared, which was then digested on a water bath for about 1½ hr. This was then filtered, washed well with ethanol, and dried in vacuum over CaCl_2 . The compound did not respond to any test for sulphate. {Found: V, 11.95; N, 33.58; C, 46.50; H, 3.80. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_3)_2]$ requires V, 12.29; N, 33.74; C, 46.28; H, 3.85%}.

Oxo-bis-benziminazole-2-carboxylato-vanadium (IV) Monohydrate.—Aqueous vanadyl sulphate (0.25 g.) was added to an ethanolic solution of benziminazole-2-carboxylic acid. The blue-green solution on cooling in ice-water deposited a bluish green crystalline product, which was filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol, and dried over CaCl_2 . {Found: V, 12.32; N, 13.50; H_2O (by loss at 100°), 4.20. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires V, 12.53; N, 13.76; H_2O , 4.42%}.

Oxo-bis-oxine-N-oxide-vanadium (IV).—An aqueous solution of VOSO_4 (0.25 g. in 10 ml water) was added slowly to a warm solution of oxine-N-oxide (0.35 g.) in dilute acetic acid (15-20 ml). The green solution formed deposited a dark olive-green crystalline substance at pH (ca.) 2-3. This was then digested on a water bath for a short while, filtered, washed well with water, and dried in vacuum over CaCl_2 . {Found: V, 12.80; N, 7.21. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{NO}_2)_2]$ requires V, 13.11; N, 7.19%}.